

**COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF METHODS FOR
CONSTRUCTING COMPLETE REMOVABLE DENTURE.**

Ruziyeva S.S.

Tashkent medical academy

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Treatment of patients with complete absence of teeth is one of the most difficult problems of orthopedic dentistry, which still does not lose its importance. In patients over 75 years of age, the prevalence of complete absence of teeth can reach 70%. In addition to chewing and speech disorders, patients with complete absence of teeth often have asymmetry of the face, a decrease in the height of the lower part of the face, disorders of the masticatory muscles, pathologies of the temporomandibular joint, etc.

Especially the difficulty of patients to adapt to it after wearing prosthesis is one of the problems of dentistry. The reason for this is poor stabilization of the prostheses. Another complication that occurs after prosthetics is mucosal diseases that develop on the basis of a fully removable prosthesis.

Many different methods and devices have been proposed to reduce the negative effects of fully removable prostheses and to improve their fixation, divided into methods based on orthopedic effects, conservative methods, methods based on a combination of different methods of exposure. However, the use of these methods is limited due to various factors: low clinical efficiency, high complexity of manipulations and excessive traumatization of tissues, general body limitations and lack of stable results. Based on these, it is important for us to come up with functional and materially convenient methods that suit patients in every way.

Research methods

1. Methods of clinical examination in complete toothless patients.
2. Speech tests.
3. Method of stereognosis.
4. Patients to fill out a questionnaire.

We divided complete toothless patients into main and control groups. 8 patients were selected in each group. Then, 8 patients in the main group were fitted with large dentures with a removable denture base. 8 patients in the control group were given prostheses made in a traditional way, i.e. some of them were not large-sized. Prostheses placed in patients using several methods were compared and results were obtained.

One of the methods used is the method of determining chewing efficiency, and I would like to record the results. This method was performed in each of the patients and the chewing index was determined by the following method.

$$\text{Ch. I.} = \frac{m}{t} = \frac{800}{14} = 57,1 \text{ mgs}$$

Here, m- chewed nut mass,
800- nut mass

t- chewing time

Chewing efficiency is found by multiplying the results obtained from patients, that is, the chewing index by 100, and dividing it by the normal chewing index. Accordingly, the results are shown in the diagram below.

Chewing performance indicators of patients in the main group:

Chewing performance indicators of patients in the control group:

According to the results of the chart, the patients in the main group have higher chewing efficiency than the patients in the control group.

Conclusion:

1. The process of final adaptation of patients to complete removable prostheses made according to the improved methods is faster in comparison with the generally accepted method of prosthetics, and the degree of their fixation, stabilization and equilibrium is higher than in case of arbitrary formation of the base and tooth rows.
2. In retreatment of the majority of elderly and old people with complete absence of teeth, the technology of manufacturing new prostheses with gradual, gradual correction of their structure should be applied; oral stereo gnosis before the beginning of treatment can be a certain prognostic sign of adaptation to the prosthesis.

3. Application of the functional method of prosthetics for patients with complete tooth loss, especially with the use of volumetric modeling in difficult clinical conditions, improves the quality of prosthetic treatment, which is confirmed by the results of masticatory and speech tests.

4. The methods of studying the results of adaptation to complete removable prostheses (patient assessment, compliance with aesthetic norms, ability to eat a variety of foods, chewing index, speech tests, stereognosia), proved to be adequate and can be used for comparative determination of their quality.

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